

Adopted 9/1/1994; Revised: 1/11/96, 10/22/97, 9/9/99, 6/8/00, 6/13/03, 7/19/08, 12/11/08, 2/17/11, 1/9/13, 4/29/16

Bylaws of the PHENIX Collaboration

I. Collaboration Membership

1. Members

Scientists, engineers and students making a significant contribution to the PHENIX collaboration are eligible to be members of the Collaboration. Members in good standing (MGS) are those individuals who are associated with a PHENIX institution and who have contributed significantly to the PHENIX experiment. Beginning in 2016, there will be two six-month MGS blocks per year. For example, MGS16A for January to June and MGS16B for July to December.

2. Institutions

Institutions (universities or laboratories) shall be admitted to the Collaboration or removed from it by the Institutional Board upon recommendation of the Executive Council. Normally, each institution shall have at least two scientists who are eligible to be members. It is expected that a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between the Institution and the Collaboration shall be implemented within a reasonable time. It is also expected that all PHENIX institutions shall fulfill their responsibility for an appropriate share of shifts and other service work as determined by the IB.

II. Institutional Board

1. Membership

Membership shall consist of one PHENIX member from each collaborating institution who shall represent the membership from that institution. Each institution shall select its representative. Substitution of representatives at meetings shall be allowed.

2. Function

The Institutional Board shall deal with general issues which concern the Collaboration as a whole. Examples include the organization and the governance of the Collaboration, adoption of bylaws, admission of new institutions to the Collaboration, publication policy and issues affecting graduate students.

The Spokesperson or Co-Spokespersons shall be elected by the Institutional Board every three years, and two or more members of the Executive Council shall be elected by the Institutional Board every year.

3. Meetings

Meetings of the Institutional Board shall be held at least twice per year, normally in conjunction with Collaboration meetings. The meetings shall be open and chaired by the Spokesperson(s) or by their designated representative.

Consideration of proposed changes to these bylaws and the adoption of a list of nominees for the position of Spokesperson(s) and for members of the Executive Council shall take place at scheduled meetings of the Institutional Board. Notice of at least four weeks shall be given indicating the time and place of the meeting and the nature of the issues to be considered.

4. Voting

The Institutional Board shall make decisions based on a simple majority of voting members. Voting members are IB members from active institutions with at least one individual who has qualified as MGS within at least one of the two previous blocks. Both single-person tickets for Spokesperson and paired-tickets for Co-Spokespersons are allowed in the same election, but the same individual may not be a candidate on more than one ticket.

Proxy voting shall be allowed. Electronic voting on issues and candidates presented for a vote shall be allowed. Scheduled meetings of the Institutional Board shall always allow remote participation with votes cast by IB members or proxies. However, voting by electronic ballot shall also be allowed within 2 weeks after the meeting.

III. Executive Council

1. Membership

The Executive Council shall have 12 or more PHENIX members. The following members of PHENIX Management shall be members of the Executive Council: Spokesperson(s), Deputy Spokesperson(s), and Operations Director. Six or more members shall be elected by the Institutional Board. Two or more members shall be appointed by the Spokesperson(s) and shall serve at their discretion. Appointments by the Spokesperson(s) should be approved by the IB. It is intended that members of the Executive Council be chosen for their scientific judgment, technical expertise, and commitment to the experiment, not as representatives of any particular institution or detector subsystem. All elected members of the Executive Council shall serve for a period of three years.

2. Function

The Executive Council shall establish scientific priorities for the experiment. It shall review and act on recommendations of the Spokesperson(s) and/or of PHENIX Management regarding all issues of major importance to the Collaboration.

The Executive Council may appoint review committees and task forces to provide advice on technical, scientific and technological decisions, as needed.

3. Meetings

Meetings of the Executive Council shall be held at least once every two months and shall be chaired by the Spokesperson(s), or by their designated representative. Minutes of the Executive Council shall be made available to the collaboration.

IV. Spokesperson(s)

The Spokesperson or Co-Spokespersons shall be elected by the Institutional Board for a three-year renewable term. There is no limit on the number of terms the Spokesperson(s) may serve.

The Spokesperson(s) may appoint review committees and task forces to provide advice on technical, scientific and technological decisions, as needed.

V. Deputy Spokesperson

One or more Deputy Spokespersons shall be proposed by the Spokesperson(s) and shall be approved by the Executive Council and by the Institutional Board.

VI. Operations Director

The term of the Operations Director is indefinite. The Executive Council or the Institutional Board or BNL management may move to change the Operations Director. If the Executive Council, the Institutional Board, and BNL management determine that a change of Operations Director is warranted (or upon the resignation of the Operations Director) a search committee shall be established by the Executive Council. Upon recommendation of the Search Committee, a new Operations Director shall be appointed by BNL management with the concurrence of the Executive Council and of the Institutional Board.

The Operations Director may appoint review committees and task forces to provide advice on technical, scientific, and technological decisions, as needed.

VII. Deputy Operations Director(s)

One or more Deputy Operations Directors shall be proposed by the Spokesperson in consultation with the Operations Director and approved by the Executive Council.

VIII. Detector Council

1. Membership

The members of the Detector Council shall be proposed by the Operations Director with the concurrence of the Deputy Operations Director(s) and they shall be approved by the Executive Council. Each member of the Detector Council shall have responsibility for a detector subsystem or for a specific detector-related or upgrade activity.

2. Function

The Detector Council shall advise management on design, performance, construction, integration, and operation issues for both the existing detector and for upgrades to the detector.

The Detector Council may appoint review committees and task forces to provide advice on technical, scientific and technological decisions, as needed.

3. Meetings

Meetings of the Detector Council shall be held at the discretion of the Operations Director or the Deputy Operations Director, normally at intervals of six to eight weeks. The meetings shall be chaired by the Operations Director, the Deputy Operations Director, or their designated representative.

IX. Definition of Individual Responsibilities

The responsibilities of members of the Detector Council as individuals and of those members of PHENIX Management referred to in these Bylaws shall be as defined in the PHENIX Operations Plan.

X. Physics Working Groups

1. Formation of Physics Working Groups

Physics Working Groups and their Conveners and Co-conveners shall be proposed by the Spokesperson(s) and approved by the Executive Council. Termination of any Physics Working Group shall be proposed by the Spokesperson(s) and approved by the Executive Council.

2. Function

The Physics Working Groups shall develop, certify, and prepare for publication all official PHENIX physics results.

3. Meetings

Meetings of all Physics Working Groups shall normally take place at least once per month at the discretion of the respective Conveners and/or Co-conveners.

XI. Adoption and Revisions

These bylaws were adopted by the PHENIX Institutional Board on September 1, 1994. Revisions to articles III, VII, and X (to eliminate the position of Project Engineer) were adopted on January 11, 1996. Revisions to article III, part 1 and to article VII (to add a second Deputy Project Director and the PHENIX-J Liaison to the Executive Council, thereby increasing EC membership to “up to 14” members) were adopted on October 22, 1997. Revisions to Article I, parts 1 and 2 (to define “Members in good standing” and institutional responsibilities) were adopted on September 9, 1999.

Extensive changes to the Bylaws were adopted on June 9, 2000 to make the Bylaws consistent with the recommendations of a Task Force, which was given the charge to restructure PHENIX as it changed from a construction project to the operations phase. Operations Manager replaces Project Director. PHENIX Management replaces Project Management. Upgrades Manager replaces two Deputy Project Directors. Appointment of one or more Deputy Spokespersons is now mandatory. The Executive Council is reconfigured to consist of four members of Project Management, two members appointed by the Spokesperson and six or more members elected by the Institutional Board. The method of election of members of the Executive Council is changed to allow the election of two or more new Executive Council members each year. The scope of the Detector Council is expanded to include operations issues. The Physics Working Groups are addressed in a new section X. The number of this section is changed to XI. A temporary (with validity until the end of 2000) addendum to the Bylaws was also adopted on June 9, 2000 to initiate the changes listed above.

Changes to the Bylaws were adopted on June 13, 2003 to allow “one or more” Deputy Spokesperson(s) and consequently 12 “or more” members of the PHENIX Executive Council; on July 19, 2008 to make a change in the definition of members from “graduate students” to simply “students;” on December 11, 2008 to change PHENIX Management title from “Operations Manager” to “Operations Director” in sections VI, VII, and VIII and “Upgrades Manager” to “One or more Deputy Operations Directors” in section VII.

Minor changes to the Bylaws were adopted on February 17, 2011 to state that “with advance notice from the Spokesperson, additional IB meetings may be scheduled with remote participation and voting by electronic ballot within 2 weeks after the meeting.”

Significant changes to the Bylaws were adopted on January 9, 2013 to allow the election of either an individual Spokesperson or paired-ticket of Co-Spokespersons, an explicit statement of procedures for a single-ticket election, and to allow remote participation and voting during IB meetings.

Changes to the Bylaws were adopted on April 29, 2016 to delete the sentence about IB approval needed to participate in another RHIC collaboration; to define two six-month MGS blocks (A and B) per year, instead of one; and to define Voting Member.